

MATRIX DAMAGE IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES UNDER BIAXIAL STRESS

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1 Introduction

While fiber reinforced polymers have gained broad acceptance in commercial and military applications, little consensus exists in selecting methodologies to describe strength. Soden et al. conducted one of the most comprehensive studies for the purpose of assessing the predictive capabilities of some of the most prominent failure theories of composite materials [1]. They found poor agreement generally between failure criteria and experimental results, even to predict the onset of damage. Most of the theories were incapable of predicting the large deformations observed experimentally where the behavior was dominated by the matrix. The Zinoviev model was one of the best at predicting final failure strain and deformations of laminates. The present work is concerned with pressure vessels made from a $[\pm\theta]$ bias orientation, which tend to exhibit a matrix dominated failure. The following applies the Maximum Strain Criterion to cylindrical coupons subjected to an internal pressure. In order to model the gradual failure process phenomenological approaches were used which don't require a damage

Fig.1. Cross-sectional view of multi-axial test fixture

Table1. Elastic and strength properties of uniaxial carbon/epoxy test coupons

[0] ₆		[90] ₁₆		[+/-45] _{2S}	
E ₁ (GPa)	S _L ⁽⁺⁾ (GPa)	E ₂ (GPa)	S _T ⁽⁺⁾ (MPa)	G ₁₂ (GPa)	S _{LT} (MPa)
138	2.30	9.33	43.4	4.56	91.9

law to correlate the crack density with the material property degradation.

2 Experimental Work

2.1 Material characterization

Mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy samples were determined by standard uniaxial tests which were performed on flat coupons (25 mm wide and 200 mm long) with three different layups, [0]₄, [90]₁₆, [+45]_{2S}. The average values of the elastic stiffness and strength are reported in Table 1.

2.2 Multi-axial test

A test fixture was designed to apply controlled levels of uniform biaxial stress in a cylindrical coupon. While cylindrical coupons are not common, numerous applications can be found in the literature describing their use. The fixture was capable of introducing axial, hoop and torsional stress in the test coupon as shown in Fig. 1 [2].

The test coupon was designed analogous to a dog bone specimen. A tab thickness and taper angle were adjusted to minimize stress concentrations in the coupon. Finite element simulation was used to examine the stress concentration in the test specimen. A tab thickness of 3.8 mm and a taper of 8° was observed to introduce a maximum stress concentration of 6%. Test coupons were fabricated from a carbon/epoxy pre-preg (T600:125/33) using

Table 2. Failure mode and first ply failure strain for each test coupon and fiber orientation

Coupon #	Fiber Orientation				
	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°
	(γ_{12})	(γ_{12})	(γ_{12})	(ϵ_2)	(ϵ_2)
1	0.0066	0.0065	N/A	0.0060	0.0057
2	0.0047	0.0056	0.0061	0.0065	0.0060
3	0.0059	0.0054	0.0055	0.0057	0.0055
Average	0.0057	0.0059	0.0058	0.0061	0.0057

hand lay-up and an autoclave cure. The ply geometry was selected to provide continuous fiber reinforcement over the length of the part. Following the initial cure, e-glass/epoxy cloth pre-preg was applied to the ends of the specimen. The tabs were cured and machined to mate with the test fixture as shown in Fig. 2. The coupon had an inside diameter of 50 mm and a length of 250 mm.

2.3 Experiment Results

Fig. 3 shows the axial stress-strain data for a representative sample of the five fiber orientations considered. Negative axial strains were observed for fiber angles less than 55° due to the large poisson effect from the hoop stress. Except for the 55° laminate, each of the coupons exhibited non-linear response consistent with a first ply failure mode. The nonlinear stress-strain response was attributed to the polymer matrix. At the fiber angle 55°, for instance, where netting analysis shows load in the matrix is minimized, the stress-strain response was linear.

3 Discussion

3.1 First ply failure

The lamina failure analysis was based on the Maximum Strain Failure criterion which has shown

Fig.2. Machined test specimen with end tabs.

good agreement by many researchers [3,4]. Usually the allowable strains are determined from uniaxial tests of a unidirectional laminate however we used experimental biaxial data to define the initial yielding strain, so there is no need to apply an in situ factor. The strain-stress results were transformed into the material coordinate system for each fiber orientation. The stress-strain curves in the material principle direction showed two distinct failure modes. For the 40°, 45° and 50° fiber angles the dominant failure mode was shear while for the 55° and 60° the failure mode was in the transverse direction. The first ply failure (FPF) was defined from the intercept of the stress-strain curve in the material direction with a linear offset line of 800 $\mu\epsilon$. The FPF strains and failure modes are presented in Table 2 for each test coupon and fiber orientation.

3.2 Modulus Reduction

The nonlinear response of the laminates was described through the decomposition of the stress strain curve into piece-wise linear increments. The lamina stiffness remained constant until the first ply failure.

When strain in the transverse or shear direction exceeded its elastic limit, the lamina stiffness in that direction decreased until the simulated strain at the end of the increment coincided with experiment. The

Fig. 3. The axial stress-strain response for each fiber orientation, Symbols denote experimental results, the straight lines are from the empirical modulus reduction functions and dotted lines are from the Zinoviev model

stiffness matrix was updated at the end of each stress increment. The value of the stiffness and its corresponding principal strain were recorded. The entire response of the laminate was determined from the cumulative summation of all increments and the stiffness reduction was obtained throughout the entire loading history. The average modulus from test coupons for each failure mode was used as a stiffness reduction function as shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5.

To test the modulus reduction functions, $E_2(\epsilon_2)$ and $G_{12}(\gamma_{12})$, the pressure vessel stress-strain history was reconstructed for each fiber orientation. This was done in the material coordinate system according to

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix}_N = \sum_{i=0}^N \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -v_{21}/E_2(\epsilon_2)_{i-1} & 0 \\ -v_{21}/E_2(\epsilon_2)_{i-1} & 1/E_2(\epsilon_2)_{i-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/G_{12}(\gamma_{12})_{i-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} d\sigma \\ 2d\sigma \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $d\sigma = 100$ kPa, was the stress increment. The strains were then transformed into the coupon coordinate system from which the stress was computed to compare with the experimental results as shown in Fig. 3. The comparison of the experimental and predicted results is also favorable, confirming that limit criteria, such as the Maximum Strain Criterion, can be used to describe matrix dominated failure of composite laminates subjected to multiaxial stress.

Fig.4. shear modulus reduction, the dotted line represents Zinoviev model and the straight line is the experimental measured modulus change

3.3 The Zinoviev Model

The Zinoviev theory employs a Maximum stress failure criterion for the onset of failure and uses lamina elastic-perfect plastic behavior for progressive failure [5]. Zinoviev assumes that the unidirectional ply within the composite laminate deforms elastically in the fiber direction until the longitudinal stress reaches its ultimate value, when the ply is assumed to be broken. The behaviors of the ply in the transverse and shear directions as shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 are elastic perfect-plastic. Using the yield strength from the biaxial offset method, the Zinoviev model is compared with the experimental and simulated results in Fig. 3. The experimental data show higher stiffness after the first ply failure than the perfect plastic simulation of the Zinoviev model. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 compare the material degradation curves based on the Zinoviev model and experiment. The shear modulus reduction behavior based on the Zinoviev model is similar to experiment; however the transverse modulus reduction is remarkably different.

3.4 Stress strain curve simulation for uniaxial test

For a single lamina under transverse and shear uniaxial loading, the stress strain curves based on the empirical modulus reduction functions are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. The transverse loading of the unidirectional lamina shows two basic regions; namely, the elastic and post yield regions. In the post yield region the transverse strength is not constant

Fig.5. Transverse modulus reduction, the dotted line represents Zinoviev model and the straight line is the experimental measured modulus change

but decreases at a nearly constant rate. This post yield loss of strength has also been observed in unidirectional tests [6]. In the shear direction the lamina showed hardening behavior in the post yield region. While the aforementioned shear and transverse yield response is surprising, it is not entirely unexpected. In shear, for instance, frictional effects, as fracture surfaces interact, can account for hardening. In the transverse direction, on the other hand, cracks tend to open, which limit load paths and lead to diminished strength.

4 Conclusion

The foregoing has considered composite pressure vessels with a bias fiber orientation ranging from 40° to 60°. The lack of fiber reinforcement in the primary loading directions produced matrix dominated failure modes in all the test coupons. Coupons with a fiber orientation of 50° or less exhibited a shear failure mode, while coupons with a fiber orientation of 55° or more had a transverse failure mode. The first ply failure strain and modulus reduction was relatively constant for the each failure mode. The biaxial stress-strain curves were simulated for each fiber angle using the Zinoviev model. The Zinoviev results showed good agreement with experiment when the laminate first ply strength were used as material yielding properties. In addition the reduction in transverse and shear modulus were compared with simulated results that showed the Zinoviev assumption for perfect plastic behavior could be used in the shear direction although a hardening behavior was more compatible

Fig.6. The uniaxial shear stress-strain response, the straight line represents Zinoviev model and the dotted line is from the modulus reduction function (Fig.4 and Fig.5)

with experiment. In the transverse direction the simulated results showed that the perfectly plastic assumption should be revised; it seems that a negative tangent modulus should be used. The results suggest that the maximum strain can be effectively used to describe matrix dominated failure in fiber reinforced composites.

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Fig.7. The uniaxial transverse stress-strain response, the straight line represents Zinoviev model and the dotted line is from the modulus reduction function (Fig.4 and Fig.5)